

1 Cross-mapping of terms used in chemical risk assessment with 2 those used in systematic review: research protocol

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41 Disclaimer

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49 Abstract

50 The focus on implementation of systematic review (SR) principles in chemical risk
51 assessments (CRAs) is growing as it has the potential to advance the rigour and
52 transparency of the CRAs. However, the SR and CRA communities use their own specific
53 terminologies. Understanding the meaning of core SR and CRA terms and where they
54 overlap is critical for application of SR methods and principles in CRAs. Moreover, it will
55 increase the possibility for cross-sectorial collaboration, avoid misunderstandings, and
56 improve communication among risk assessors, researchers, and policy makers.

57 We present a process for the cross-mapping of core CRA terms and core SR terms. Core
58 terms for study appraisal, evidence synthesis and integration used in the SR and CRA
59 communities will be included. The outcome will be an overview of how core SR terms map

60 onto core CRA terms and vice versa, and a description of the relationship and conceptual
61 overlap between the terms.

62 The cross-mapping is divided in three phases, where in the first phase the core SR and CRA
63 terms will be identified. In the second phase, existing SR and CRA definitions will be
64 mapped. In the third phase, descriptions of the relationship and conceptual overlap between
65 the terms will be derived. The third phase will include weekly one-hour online meetings for
66 SR and CRA experts.

67 Key words

68 Conceptual overlap, cross-mapping, definitions, interoperability, terminology.

69 1. Introduction

70 Chemical risk assessments (CRAs) should be evidence-based, which means that they are
71 grounded in a comprehensive and rigorous, transparent and objective analysis of all
72 evidence relating to the assessment task. Applying systematic review (SR) principles in
73 CRAs has become an established methodology for achieving this goal, from its first practical
74 introduction in 2013-14 (NTP OHAT, 2015; Woodruff and Sutton, 2014), its popularisation in
75 the following few years (Hoffmann et al., 2017; Whaley et al., 2016), and its wider uptake by
76 national and international risk assessment agencies including US EPA (EPA, 2022; EPA,
77 2023), EFSA (EFSA, 2010; EFSA et al., 2017a), and WHO (WHO, 2021).

78 Because SR and CRA methodologies were developed independently of each other, the SR
79 and CRA communities use their own specific terminologies and language. Numerous SRs
80 performed as part of CRAs have shown that these terminologies often are analogous to
81 each other or overlapping, but rarely the same or directly translatable. Also, often a reporting
82 checklist, like the PRISMA checklist, have not been included. It can therefore be difficult to
83 understand which SR method (or to what level/extent) is applied in the CRAs (i.e., whether a
84 given framework or application is sufficiently rigorous to be described as “systematic”) and
85 may be impeding the understanding and therefore potentially slowing the uptake of SR
86 methods in the CRA community.

87 In this project, we will analyse conceptual overlap and differences between the core CRA
88 terms of SR and CRA. This way, we aim to increase the interoperability of SR and CRA
89 terminologies by improving the understanding of the meaning of and the relationships
90 between the core terms of the respective domains.

91 1.1 Project governance

92 This project is a part of the “[Next generation risk assessment in practice](#)” project (VKM,
93 2023) which is included in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from
94 Chemicals ([PARC](#); Project 101057014)”. The participants in this project include the
95 members of the research team and the members of the scientific advisory group (SAG). A
96 project group (PG) has been established with the responsibility for drafting the protocol and
97 performing the study.

98 2 Methods

99 2.1 Study design

100 A cross-mapping of core SR and CRA terms will be performed to explore the relationship
101 between the terms and to identify conceptual overlaps. By “core” we mean terms denoting
102 key concepts in the study appraisal, evidence synthesis, and evidence integration steps of
103 systematic reviews. For CRAs and SRs, the scope is limited to methods for quantitative
104 systematic review of health effects of interventions and exposures and methods for evidence
105 synthesis. The project is divided into three phases as shown in Figure 1.

106

107 **Figure 1.** Overview of the three phases and the timeline for the cross-mapping between core
108 systematic review and core chemical risk assessment terms. Abbreviations: CRA, chemical
109 risk assessment; SR, systematic review.

110 The timeline for the project and estimated duration for each phase are shown in Figure 1.
111 Phase 3 will include weekly one-hour online meetings for the discussion of the descriptions
112 of SR and CRA term relationships and conceptual overlap, and the anticipated duration of
113 this phase is 3 to 5 months.

114 2.2 Phase 1: Cataloguing core terms in SR and CRA terminologies

115 The objective is to catalogue core SR and CRA terms that are used for study appraisal,
116 evidence synthesis and integration.

117 **Creating longlists of SR and CRA terms**

118 A selection of handbooks, guidance documents and glossaries from different sources will be
119 used to identify core SR and CRA terms (Table 1). Two persons from the PG will
120 independently go through the documents listed in Table 1 and extract terms that are used for
121 study appraisal, evidence synthesis or evidence integration. All extracted terms will be
122 included in the longlist. The longlist of terms will be computed into Excel and will be available
123 as supplementary materials.

124 It was originally intended that the longlists would be machine generated using the Term
125 Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method. However, the PG did a pilot
126 test of the TD-IDF method on the document collection using the English Web corpus
127 enTenTen21 (Sketch Engine, 2023) as the comparator corpus, and it was found to be less
128 efficient than expected, with challenges on corpus selection, data cleaning, and optimisation
129 of term abstraction and rank ordering. We have therefore determined that manual
130 identification of terms will be done instead.

131 **Table 1.** The document collection for identification of core SR and CRA terms.

Document	Reference
SEVCO (Scientific Evidence Code System)	FEvIR Platform Version 0.80.0 (06.12.2022)
Finding What Works in Health Care: Standards for Systematic Reviews	Institute of Medicine Committee on Standards for Systematic Reviews of Comparative Effectiveness (2011)
JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis	Aromataris et al. (2020)

Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making	EFSA (2010)
Methodological Expectations of Cochrane Interventions Reviews (MECIR)	Higgins et al. (2023)
Glossary of Terms in The Cochrane Collaboration, Version 4.2.5	Cochrane Collaboration (2005)
Handbook for Conducting a Literature Based Health Assessment Using OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration	NTP OHAT (2019)
Framework for the use of systematic review in chemical risk assessment	WHO (2021)
Guiding Principles and Key Elements for Establishing a Weight of Evidence for Chemical Assessment	OECD (2019)
ORD Staff Handbook for Developing IRIS Assessments	EPA (2022)
Guidance on the assessment of the biological relevance of data in scientific assessments	EFSA et al. (2017b)
PRISMA 2020	Page et al. (2021)
EFSA glossary	EFSA (2024)

132

133 **Creating the final shortlist of core SR and CRA terms**

134 An expert group, consisting of a minimum four experts from the PG and SAG, who have
 135 experience within SR, CRA or both fields will be created.

136 The expert group members will individually screen the longlist which contains both CRA and
 137 SR terms in Excel. The experts can also add additional terms they believe should be
 138 included but are not on the longlist. For each term, the expert group members will rate their
 139 level of agreement using a 5-point Likert scale (5 indicates strong agreement, whereas 1

140 indicates strong disagreement) towards two statements: 1) This term is a core CRA term for
141 study appraisal, evidence integration and/or evidence synthesis, 2) This term is a core SR
142 term for study appraisal, evidence integration and/or evidence synthesis.

143 Terms scored “4” or “5” on the Likert scale by one or more members of the expert group will
144 be considered as core terms and included in the shortlist.

145 The shortlists will be presented and discussed in PG and SAG meetings to identify i) terms
146 on the shortlist that are not related to study appraisal, evidence synthesis and integration
147 process, and ii) additional terms that should be included. The final shortlists will be prepared
148 by the PG and be available as supplementary materials. Information on the cumulative score
149 (Likert scale scoring) will also be available.

150 In the case that many core terms are identified and there is a need for prioritisation, the
151 cumulative scores (Likert scale) will be used to prioritise terms to be included in the cross-
152 mapping.

153 2.3 Phase 2: Preparing a list of existing definitions of SR and CRA terms

154 The objective of this phase is to prepare a list of a representative range of definitions of the
155 core SR and CRA terms.

156 The definitions for the SR and CRA terms will be primarily collected from glossaries,
157 guidance’s and handbooks listed in Table 1. However, if the definitions are not listed in those
158 documents other sources might be used, which will be identified by an Internet search or
159 brainstorming within the PG and SAG. The definitions of the core SR and CRA terms will be
160 extracted by one PG member and checked by another PG member. Each extracted
161 definition will be tagged with from which source it was extracted from. The table will be made
162 available as supplementary materials.

163 2.5 Phase 3: Identifying conceptual overlap between CRA and SR terms

164 The objective is to identify areas of conceptual overlap and difference between CRA terms
165 and SR terms. The cross-mapping will be done via a consensus process involving an expert
166 group with PG and SAG members and additional experts (see section 2.6) self-identifying as
167 having relevant CRA and/or SR expertise. The main steps in the cross-mapping are shown
168 in Table 2. A more detailed overview of the steps is included in the Supplementary materials
169 (Table S-1). The approach is adapted from the consensus process used in the development
170 of the SEVCO methods ontology and the GRADE Ontology (Alper et al., 2024; Alper et al.,
171 2021).

172 **Table 2.** The four main steps in the cross-mapping process.

Step	What
<p>1. Identification of relationships between core CRA terms and core SR terms.</p>	<p>PG will map which terms are related.</p>
<p>2. Assembling an expert group with PG members, SAG members, and additional experts, all self-identifying as having relevant SR and/or CRA expertise.</p>	<p>The relationship between terms is discussed in the expert group. Descriptions of the relationships between the terms will be drafted according to the discussion.</p>
<p>3. Identification of agreement on discussed descriptions (approval of the draft statements from step 2).</p>	<p>The experts vote (anonymously, online) “agree” or “not agree” on approval of the draft statement from step 2.</p> <p>The criteria for agreement are: i) at least 5 members voted AND ii) all votes were for “agree”.</p> <p>If an agreement is reached, stop here.</p> <p>If no agreement is reached, proceed to step 4.</p>
<p>4. Suggestion of changes to the descriptions where no agreement was reached.</p>	<p>The result of the vote is discussed in the expert group and redrafted when needed. Participants will vote (online) “agree” or “not agree” on each discussed statement. The criteria for agreement for descriptions of relationships between the terms that are discussed for the second time are: i) at least 5 members voted AND ii) at least 80% of the votes were for “agree”.</p> <p>If an agreement is reached, stop here.</p> <p>If no agreement is reached, proceed to step 3.</p>

	Steps 3 and 4 are repeated a maximum of two times. If agreement is not reached, no statement of the relationship between the CRA and the SR terms will be created. However, information on the difficulties and suggested descriptions will be included as supplementary materials
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173

174 2.6 The expert groups participating in phase 3

175 The experts participating in the online meetings will be PG and SAG members and additional
176 experts self-identifying as having relevant SR or CRA expertise. Recruitment of the
177 additional experts will be done by PG and SAG members via their national and international
178 SR and CRA networks. Anyone self-identifying as having the relevant expertise can sign up
179 at any time. Expert group participants will be sent project updates, in particular notifications
180 of when terms are open for vote, by email. Votes will be cast by email to the PG member
181 tasked with facilitating the discussion and voting process. The facilitator will anonymise the
182 votes to the rest of the PG and expert group.

183 Following the additional experts first participation, they will be asked to fill out a short
184 questionnaire with questions about their affiliation, type of profession, country of residence,
185 gender, age, and number of years of experience with SRs and CRAs (phase 3). Information
186 on race or ethnicity will not be collected because in Norway this information falls under the
187 category of “sensitive personal data” and on a general note this type of data is not legal to be
188 collected or handled.

189 Everyone on the mailing list will receive meeting documents in front of the meetings.
190 Everyone that participated in a meeting will be asked to participate in the voting after the
191 meeting. The votes will not be anonymous for the PG but will be anonymised in the
192 manuscript.

193 Expert Group members are eligible to be co-authors if they i) vote and/or comment on at
194 least ten terms or cross-mappings in total, and ii) reviews the manuscript. Expert group
195 members not eligible to be co-authors will be listed in the acknowledgements. No financial
196 compensation or other incentives are offered for the participation as additional expert.

197 3 Anticipated results

198 In this section we describe how the result of the study will be presented in the results section
199 of the finalised manuscript. All other results will be made available as supplementary
200 materials.

201 3.1 Core SR and CRA terms

202 A list of core terms in the SR and CRA terminologies, and the Likert scale scoring, will be
203 presented. A table illustrating a proposed way to present the results is included in the
204 Supplementary materials (Table S-2).

205 3.2 SR and CRA term definitions

206 The definitions of SR and CRA core terms and their synonyms will be presented. Tables
207 illustrating the presentation of the catalogued definitions of SR and CRA terms are included
208 in the Supplementary materials (Tables S-3 and S-4). The presentation of participant
209 characteristics for the expert group participating in phase 3 is illustrated in the
210 Supplementary materials (Table S-6).

211 3.4 Conceptual overlap between core SR and core CRA terms

212 Descriptions of the relationship between CRA terms and SR terms will be presented. Tables
213 illustrating how this information will be presented are included in the Supplementary
214 materials. The proposed presentation of the cross-mapping of CRA terms on the SR terms is
215 shown in the Supplementary materials (Table S-5). The proposed presentation of the SR
216 terms and the related CRA terms and the conceptual overlap is shown in the Supplementary
217 materials (Table S-6). The proposed presentation of participant characteristics for the expert
218 group participating in phase 3 is shown in the Supplementary materials (Table S-7).

219 4 Limitations

220 The methods described in this protocol are considered to provide a grounded process
221 towards a common understanding for the meaning of these terms without being too time-
222 consuming. A consequence may be that not all relevant terms from all SR and CRA
223 communities will be included.

224 While we attempt to involve a broad and diverse group of experts from several institutions in
225 this project, it is possible that we will not be able to recruit participants from all relevant
226 institutions within the SR and CRA communities. However, being able to distribute
227 information through the networks of both the PG and the SAG, we expect to recruit
228 participants from several relevant institutions.

229 For the online group discussions in Phase 3, there is a risk for some persons to dominate
230 the discussion. To reduce this, an experienced and neutral moderator (PW) will facilitate the
231 discussions. Anonymous voting online should also allow for more ease at disagreeing with
232 strong personalities and participants assumed higher in a social hierarchy. Because we are
233 aiming at a high level of consensus, voting will give all participants the opportunity to
234 contribute over several rounds of development of the cross-map, with the requirement that
235 their comments are considered in each round of discussion. If any participants feel their
236 comments are not responded to, they can vote “no” in the next round of voting. Also, we are
237 planning for a diverse mix of experiences and backgrounds in the group.

238 Dissemination

239 The outcome of this project will be published in a scientific journal.

240 Abbreviations

241 CRA: chemical risk assessment

242 PG: project group

243 SAG: scientific advisory group

244 SEVCO: Scientific Evidence Code System

245 SR: systematic review

246 Definition

247 **Core terms** are in this project defined as terms denoting key concepts in the study
248 appraisal, evidence synthesis, and evidence integration steps of systematic reviews.

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255 Ethical considerations

256 Application for ethical approval will be submitted to the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

257 Declaration of interests

258 Completed declaration of interest forms for each author are available as supplementary
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260 authorship, and/or publication of this protocol.

261 Authors contribution

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264 **Funding acquisition:** Camilla Svendsen and Gro H. Mathisen.

265 **Methodology:** Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, and Paul Whaley.

266 **Project administration:** Camilla Svendsen and Gro H. Mathisen.

267 **Supervision:** Paul Whaley.

268 **Visualization:** Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, and Paul Whaley.

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